

Comparative Assessment and Evaluation of Power Output of Different Types of Solar Tracking Mechanism

Pruthviraj Pratap Rahane¹, Dr.Siddappa Mahadev Kho²

[1] Assistant Professor, Department of Mechanical Engineering, Pillai College of Engineering, New Panvel, University of Mumbai, MS-410206, India

[1] PhD Research Scholar , Department of Mechanical Engineering, Fr. C. Rodrigues Institute of Technology, Vashi, University of Mumbai, MS-400703, India

[2]Principal, Department of Mechanical Engineering, Fr. C. Rodrigues Institute of Technology, Vashi, University of Mumbai, MS-400703, India

Abstract: Harnessing the maximum solar energy emitted by the sun with the help of solar PV panel is essential in today's world to meet the continuously growing energy demand from many sectors. The proficient way of achieving this goal is to make use of such a mechanism which tracks the orientation of the sun by maintaining the normality of the incident ray with solar PV panel. This research paper presents comparative analysis of energy generation through different configurations of sun tracker i.e. fix-tilt, Single axis and Dual axis. Each configuration was tested for the period of sunshine hours to achieve the objective of maximum energy generation from the PV panel. Single axis tracking system shows percentage rise in power output by 27.57% when compared with fix tilt while the dual axis tracker shows percentage rise of 37.57% and 12.54% when compared with fix tilt and single axis respectively. It is observed from the results that dual axis tracker outperforms when compared with other types as mentioned. This study demonstrates how the type of tracker affects overall power generation and provides valuable insights for selecting the most appropriate tracking technology for diverse PV installations.

Keywords: Energy yield, dual axis, single axis, fix tilt, Solar Photovoltaic (PV) , Power

1. Introduction:

The requirement of energy is increasing by many folds every day. The use of conventional energy resources has caused the degradation of environment quality. This has made researchers find alternative clean sources of energy that meets the sustainable development objectives. Solar photovoltaic (PV) systems have emerged as one of the sources of clean energy that is widely used. Large-scale installation of PV setups drastically reduces the expenses and carbon footprint when compared with traditional fossil fuels. Despite the many advanced technologies available in the field of solar PV, the overall performance of the system depends on how efficiently panels track the sun's trajectory. Many PV installations installed world-wide utilizes fix-tilt, single axis and double axis corresponding to the site taking latitude into account. This fix-tilt improves the average solar energy collection by aligning the PV panel to the site's latitude. Fix-tilt systems are unable to track the sun's continuous movement which results in energy losses. This constraint has sparked interest in researcher's minds to develop solar tracking systems for improved alignment and energy output. Trackers are generally categorized as fix-tilt, single-axis and dual-axis. Single-axis trackers rotate panels around one axis (east–west or north–south) in order to follow the path of the sun daily as shown in figure.1.

Figure.1 Sun Movement [1]

Dual-axis trackers modify both tilt and azimuth, tracking daily and seasonal sun trajectories with precision. Dual-axis systems produce 30–40% more energy than fixed setups, and 15–25% more than single-axis. Power output remains the important criterion while evaluating tracker performance. A systematic comparative analysis is very important for selecting the suitable type of tracker for a specific site. This investigation aims at assessing performance of fix-tilt, single-axis and dual-axis trackers during sunlight hours.

S Abdallah et.al has conducted a research study on a fix-tilt system and single axis suntracking system which is operated electromechanically, reveals an increase of 22% in the

power output over the fix-tilt system [2]. Pagano M et.al has evaluated the performance of a fix-tilt and single-axis system. The study showcased the instantaneous increments in power output for a singleaxis system from 12 to 20% relative to a fixed panel [3].

Aziz d et.al presents the design and practical implementation of a simple active dual-axis solar tracker (DAST) to track the sun's movement, DAST produces 36.26% more energy compared to the fixed panel [4]. Akash S et.al have developed a PLC operated two axis sun tracking mechanism. A two axis solar tracker efficiently utilizes solar radiation and has an improvement of 30 to 40% in terms of performance over a single axis tracker system [5].

Kang li et.al focused on one-axis sun tracking PV systems utilized in building structure. A comparative study between single axis tracking and fixed PV systems reveals a 37.5% rise in energy production on sunny days [6]. Fahad et.al carried out a comparative study of three types of fixed, single and dual axis tracking systems. A substantial increase in incident energy about 25 to 40% was observed for single axis system over fix-tilt system. An increase in incident energy about 26 to 45% was observed for the dual axis tracking system over fix-tilt system [7].

Protik Das et.al have developed a single axis solar tracking mechanism making the use of stepper motor, gear motor and photo diode & mirror booster. The mirror was used as a booster to increase the efficiency and to direct the maximum quantity of sunlight on to the panel. Power output was increased by 6.4% over the fixed system [8]. Eldin et.al presented the output of the single axis tracker mechanism. The single axis tracking scenario demonstrates an increase in productivity about 8.16-16.8% when compared to the non-tracking scenario in the morning through noontime [9].

Jerin et.al have introduced an automatic dual axis solar tracker using a microcontroller that achieves an increase of up to 14% on cloudy days and up to 13% on sunny days over fix-tilt system [10]. I A Sohu et.al have designed a single axis and dual tracker mechanism using the Field Programmable Gate Array (FPGA) for maximizing the incident sunlight to strike the solar PV panel. It was found that the single axis sun tracking system attains an increase in efficiency of 23.93% and 33.23% in case of dual axis tracking when compared with fixed system [11].

Chindakham et.al have performed a study on dual axis sun tracker system utilizing light-dependent resistors (LDRs) to identify poor visibility conditions that adversely affect solar tracking performance. The dual-axis solar tracking system enhances energy production by 19.97% compared to the fixed flat-plate system and by 11.00% against the LDR-based solar tracking system [12].

Sheikh M et.al have developed the dual axis sun tracker system that produces the highest electrical energy output i.e. 21.28% more efficient than the yield from horizontal axis monthly adjustments [13].

Tarique et.al have developed a hybrid two axis sun-tracking

system that can adjust the solar panel's orientation to generate the maximum possible electrical output. The power out of panel in case of hybrid (closed loop) tracker shows percentage rise about 35% when compared with open loop tracking system [14]. Jesmin Nahar et.al have built a semi-continuous single-axis solar tracker. The performance comparison of a fixed PV system, continuous single-axis sun tracker system and a semi-continuous single-axis sun tracker was carried out. The continuous single axis system is more efficient by 1.12% than the semi-continuous single axis system [15]. Shahriar et.al conducted research on various categories of PV systems like single-axis and dual-axis tracking systems. The results recorded by the dual axis tracker system shows Power improvement of 8.21% when compared with single axis system [16]. Md H Kabir et.al investigates the performance of PV panels using a single-axis, and a dual-axis tracker controlled by an Arduino UNO system. It was found that the % rise in Power Output for dual axis tracker is 6.83% when compared to single axis tracker system [17]. Karma et.al carried out experimentation on single and dual axis trackers. The % increase in Power output for dual axis mechanism was found to be 1.14% when compared with single axis solar tracker [18].

2. Motivation:

Sun rise at east and sets at west is scientifically accurate only for two days of Equinox. The Earth is tilted at 23.5 degrees to its orbital plane around the Sun. Due to this the sun shines on different latitude and different angles throughout the year causing different seasons to occur. As Earth tilt is only 47.5 degrees in north and south direction, so majorly East-West direction should be tracked as compared to north south direction. Considering the sun's earth geometry, the sun's movement needs to be considered to harness maximum solar energy. This entraps traversing this interesting field to come up with viable solutions to improve the performance of the system. This fascinates me to explore the possibility of research to build a more appropriate mechanism which facilitates in adjusting PV panels and maintaining normality with incident rays for maximum energy conversion.

3. Research Gap:

Many aspects of solar trackers were studied by different researchers, such as the effect of different tracking strategies on the performance of the system in terms of energy yield. The literature also highlights the use of different configurations of trackers available to get high energy yield all the time by maintaining normality between sun ray and PV panel. However, upon reviewing the current literature on solar tracker it is evident that there is a

lack of comprehensive research that evaluates multiple tracker types which will help further in optimization.

4. Taxonomy of Solar Tracking System:

An experimental investigation of performance of the system using a flat-plate solar collector attached to different configurations of solar tracker were carried out. Testing of different types of sun tracker mechanisms i.e fix-tilt, Single axis and dual axis tracker were carried out for the period of Sun rise to Sun Set.

4.1 Structure of Tracker Mechanisms:

The structure of a solar tracker pertains to the organization and structural setup of components used to maximize harvesting of sunlight with the help of PV panel. A design of solar tracker consists of photovoltaic (PV) modules affixed to an adjustable frame which can tilt as per the electronic signal. The motors and actuators are the part of single and dual axis tracker. The support structure or base, and the control system for orientation are the other important components.

4.1.1 Structure of Fix tilt Solar Collector:

Following is the arrangement of a fix-tilt tracker that has been built with a 50 Watt PV panel and tested for the performance. Powder coated Aluminium has been used for building the tracker assembly. The base of the tracker is built with a 2.5 mm Aluminium box section. The main purpose of using powder coated aluminum is to avoid the rusting issue as tracker assembly is always exposed to the atmosphere. The size of base of the tracker assembly is 3 ft * 2.5 ft which provides structural support to the pillar of tracker where the PV panel is mounted. The sensor control box of the tracker is also mounted at the base as shown in figure.2.

Figure.2 Fix tilt solar collector

4.1.2 Structure of Single Axis Solar Tracker:

Following is the arrangement of a single axis tracker that has been built. The fabrication process of the same was earlier explained in section above.

Figure.3 Single axis solar tracker

In addition to the fix-tilt collector the lead screw mechanism has been incorporated in the tracker assembly shown in figure to tilt Panel in East-West direction as shown in figure.3. LM 298 Comparator is used to drive the DC motor based on signal received. These mini panels are connected with a current sensor to measure the current generated by them when sunlight falls on these panels. The current output of these mini panels are used as input signals to decide the movement of the PV panel in desired direction. The main reason behind opting for mini panel's current over LDR as input to DC motor for tilting panel is that the current sensor has analog output signal in terms of current which is easily measured by sensors while LDR measures resistance. This tracker automatically changes PV panel position depending upon intensity of sunlight throughout the day. This tracker makes the use of a closed loop feedback mechanism built with various sensors to harness sunlight from dawn and dusk. At the start of dawn the tracker activates as it acquires the supply from the battery and as soon as dusk condition is sensed by sensor PV panel returned back to its original position and kept ready for next day's cycle. All the sensors are connected to either Raspberry or Arduino Mega for processing the data and it's stored on the server. Limit switches are used on the both sides of center pillar support as shown in figure 3 to avoid excessive movement of lead screw beyond its limit preventing slipping out from the nut.

4.1.3 Structure of Dual Axis Solar Tracker:

Following is the arrangement of Dual axis tracker that has been built and tested for its performance. The fabrication process of the same was earlier explained in section 3.

Figure.4 Dual axis solar tracker.

The two lead screws have been incorporated in the tracker assembly shown in fig 4 to tilt the panel in East-West and North-South direction. Two DC motors connected to lead screws are used to provide drive to tilt the PV panel to achieve optimal tilt. Four Mini panels as shown in figure above for both axes. The ADXL345 is a 3-axis digital accelerometer used to measure acceleration in X, Y, and Z directions as shown in figure.5.

Figure.5 ADXL 345

4.2 Electronic Framework of Solar Tracker:

The developed system is divided into two circuits i.e. “Arduino circuit” and “Raspberry Pi circuit” as shown in figure.6

Figure.6 Electronic framework of tracker

In an Arduino setup the Arduino Mega, which accepts input voltage ranging from 6 to 20 volt is employed. As per the previously mentioned circuit diagram, a Pyranometer and the INA 219 are connected to the Arduino Mega. The Silicon Pyranometer is used to measure solar insolation, which is later utilized to ascertain the input to the panel. The Pyranometer operates within a range of 0 to 2000 W/m². A voltage sensor module, compatible with an output voltage between 3.3V and 5V was attached to the Pyranometer which acts as a silicon transducer converting sunlight hitting the panel into voltage. The INA219 bi-directional current/power module featuring an I2C interface was employed to assess the output from a main solar panel. In addition to above, four current sensors were also connected to Arduino to estimate the current of four mini panels. This current value was later used to drive a motor for tilting the PV panel.

The Raspberry Pi 3B operates on a 5.1V / 2.5A DC input and serves as the computational core to connect with the ADXL345, DS18B20 and SI1145 sensors for data collection purposes. The purpose of integrating the Raspberry Pi 3B is to enable remote control of our system eliminating the need for physical interaction with the system's controls. The SI1145 ambient light sensor featuring an I2C interface was sourced to quantify the visible elements of sunlight. The ADXL345 module, which operates within a voltage supply range of 2.0-3.6V, is utilized to assess the tilt angle of the PV surface relative to the ground while monitoring

performance. The DS18B20 temperature sensor, with a voltage supply range of 3.3-5V tracks the temperature of the PV Panel during the testing phase.

The energy generated by the PV panel was saved in a battery rated at 12 volt and 12Ah. The electric charge retained in the battery is utilized for energizing the circuit boards. After measuring the input and output from the panel with the assistance of sensors, the electrical output of the PV panel is determined.

5. Mounting of Fix Tilt , Single Axis and Dual Axis Solar Tracker:

Investigating the performance of a solar tracker in terms of power output helps verify actual energy gain. It shows how effectively the system follows the sun to maximize electricity generation. Such analysis supports and guides design improvements. It ensures the tracker delivers expected benefits compared to fixed systems.

5.1 Mounting of Fix Tilt Solar Collector:

The tracker assembly shown in section 4.1.1, figure.2 is tested for sunshine hours and performance of the tracker is calculated later. This tracker also has an attachment to change the tilt angle manually. It enables to choose a tilt angle suited to the installation site i.e. 19° equal to latitude. 12 V DC Timer clock is used to set the dusk and dawn timing in the timer circuit. The main purpose of using a DC timer is to plug and unplug the Main Power supply during dawn and dusk. As dawn begins the timer clock acquires the supply from the battery and through a buck converter it is supplied to all electronic components of circuit as mentioned above. The buck converter was used to step down the 12V DC supply of the battery to 5 V DC which is required by electronic sensors of the circuit. The buck converter also maintains continuous supply of 5 Volt without any drop hence all sensors receive supply till dusk. The situation is recorded on the server. When Sunlight strikes photovoltaic (PV) cells made of silicon the energy from the light frees electrons, creating a flow of electric current (DC). The current and voltage output of the main panel is measured using a current and voltage sensor. These two values are later used to calculate power output.

5.2 Mounting of Single Axis Solar Tracker:

The tracker assembly shown in section 4.1.2, figure.3 is tested in the context of Power generation that will be calculated after deploying the designed algorithm as below. Setting the tracker in the single axis mode helps in achieving maximum exposure to sunlight. It helps in increasing Power output by 15 to 30 % over fix-tilt. The algorithm designed, tracks the sun by

orienting PV panel always perpendicular to sun which ultimately harness maximum of sun energy.

Figure.7 Mini Panel location

Two mini panels of 1 volt each were used and arranged accordingly as shown in figure. These panels are placed along the main Panel as shown in figure 8.

Let, Mini Panel 2 is fixed on West side of main tracking Panel

Mini Panel 4 is fixed on East side of main tracking Panel

When the sunlight falls on these mini panels it starts generating the current. By comparing the value of this generated current signal is sent to DC Motor No.1 which will tilt PV panel accordingly till current intensity recorded by Mini panel no.2 and Mini panel no.4 and vice versa. The same is highlighted in Table.1 below.

Let ,

A = Current intensity of Panel 2 (amps)

B = Current intensity of Panel 4 (amps)

Table.1 PV Panel tilting status of Single axis tracker mechanism

Mini Panel	Current intensity	Tilting of PV Panel
2	$A > B$	Anticlockwise Movement of Motor No.1 means the panel is tilted towards East side
4	$B > A$	Clockwise Movement of Motor No.1 means the panel is tilted towards West side

When Panel tries to over travel in either east or west direction it pushes the roller of limit switch mounted on its lever as shown below in figure 9.

Figure.8 Limit switch arrangement

The over travel of the PV Panel physically presses the limit switch. Due to this limit switch changes its state (NO → closed or NC → open). This change is detected by the motor controller i.e L298N and Arduino and it stops the current flow flowing towards the motor thus by preventing its rotation.

5.3 Mounting of Dual Axis Solar Tracker:

The tracker assembly shown in section 4.1.3, figure.4 is tested in the context of Power generation and will be calculated after deploying the designed algorithm as shown below. Setting the tracker in the dual axis mode helps in achieving maximum exposure to sunlight. It helps in increasing Power output by 15 to 30 % over fix-tilt. The algorithm designed, tracks the sun by orienting PV panel always perpendicular to sun which ultimately harness maximum of sun energy.

Figure.9 Mini Panel location

Four Mini panels of 1 volt each were used. These panels are placed along the main Panel as shown in figure 10.

Let, Mini Panel 1 is fixed on North side of main tracking Panel

Mini Panel 2 is fixed on West side of main tracking Panel

Mini Panel 3 is fixed on South side of main tracking Panel

Mini Panel 4 is fixed on East side of main tracking Panel

When the sunlight strikes these mini panels, it produces current relating to intensity of sunlight. These current values are later on used in algorithms to achieve optimal position of the PV panel throughout the day. The algorithm used for dual axis tracker is explained below.

Let ,

A = Current intensity of Panel 2 (amps)

B = Current intensity of Panel 4 (amps)

C = Current intensity of Panel 1 (amps)

D = Current intensity of Panel 3 (amps)

When the sunlight falls on these mini panels it starts generating the current. By comparing the value of this generated current signal is sent to two DC motors which tilt the PV panel accordingly.

Table.2 PV panel tilting status of dual axis tracker mechanism

Mini Panel	Current intensity	Tilting of PV Panel
1	$C > D$	Anticlockwise Movement of Motor No.2 means the panel is tilted towards South side
2	$A > B$	Anticlockwise Movement of Motor No.1 means the panel is tilted towards East side
3	$D > C$	Clockwise Movement of Motor No.2 means the panel is tilted towards North side
4	$B > A$	Clockwise Movement of Motor No.1 means the panel is tilted towards West side

When the PV Panel tries to over travel in the north direction it physically presses the roller of the limit switch No.2 and over travel of the PV Panel in the South direction physically presses the roller of limit switch No. 3 . Due to this limit switch changes its state (NO → closed or NC → open) as shown in figure.4. This change in limit switch state is detected by the motor controller and it stops the current flow flowing towards the motor thus by preventing its excessive rotation.

6.Performance Evaluation of Tracker Types:

When a solar panel is placed in sunlight, how much sunlight it absorbs and how much energy is converted into usable power is termed as output of PV panel. It is generally measured in terms of Watt. Solar tracker assists the PV panel to move in the direction of sun effectively during sunshine hour to improvise the capturing of maximum sunlight. How well a device can track the dynamic position of the sun through-out the day defines the amount of energy tracked systems produce. All the readings are taken for the summer season in the Month of March 2024.

6.1 Performance Evaluation of Fix Tilt Solar Collector:

Following is the observation table in which values are recorded after carrying of testing procedure as mentioned in section 5.1

Table.3 Result table of Fix tilt collector

Date	Time	Visible (Lux)	Pyranometer (W/m ²)	Temperature (°C)	Output Voltage (V)	Output Current (Amps)	Output Power (Watt)
29-3-2024	9.0.5 AM	755	391.01	40.81	19.1	1.3	24.83
29-3-2024	10.0.1 AM	758	380.58	42.81	20	1.5	30
29-3-2024	11:01:45 AM	858	215.25	55.75	20.1	1.9	40.242
29-3-2024	12:04:39 PM	959	576.6	58.25	20.8	2.07	44.505
29-3-2024	13:04:56 PM	945	576.4	57.02	19.5	2	42.58
29-3-2024	14:05:13 PM	865	550	56.8	19.8	1.7	36.159
29-3-2024	15:00:16 PM	870	495.84	51.25	19.36	1.4	27.104
29-3-2024	15:57:55 PM	862	263.93	50.44	18	1.1	19.8

The power output of a PV panel is estimated using voltage and current output measured at PV panel.

1. Power Output of PV panel (Watt):- The power output of a photovoltaic (PV) panel is the electrical power it generates from the sunlight it receives. Power Output is calculated by obtaining product value of Output Current of PV panel and Output Voltage of PV panel.

Let

O/P = Output to PV panel

I_o = Output Current recorded by PV panel (Amp)

$$= 1.3 \text{ Amp}$$

V_o = Output Voltage recorded by PV panel (V)

$$= 19.1 \text{ V}$$

Therefore,

$$O/P = V_o \times I_o$$

$$= 19.1 \times 1.3$$

$$= 24.83 \text{ Watt}$$

The total output in a day for Fix tilt at instant time (from 09:00 AM to 04:00 PM) as mentioned in Table.3 =

$$= 24.83 + 31.35 + 40.24 + 44.505 + 42.58 + 36.159 + 27.104 + 19.8$$

$$= 266.57 \text{ Wh}$$

The total output in a day for Fix tilt at instant time as mentioned in Table.3 is 266.57 Wh as calculated above

6.2 Performance Evaluation of Single Axis Solar Tracker:

Following is the observation table in which values are recorded after carrying of testing procedure as mentioned in section 5.2

Table.4 Observation table of Single Axis Solar tracker

Date	Time	Output Voltage (V)	Output Current (Amps)	Output Power (Watt)	Panel Status	Actual condition	(West) Mini panel 2 Current	(East) Mini panel 4 Current
29-4-2024	9.0.5 AM	19.5	1.62	31.59	Facing East	Panel tilted East, still tracking	0.5	0.58
29-4-2024	10.0.1 AM	20	1.85	37	Slight East	Tracking East	0.6	0.65
29-4-2024	11:01:45	20.5	2.2	45.1	leaning towards	Tracking toward center	0.8	0.85
29-4-2024	12:04:39	20.9	2.38	49.742	Horizontal (South)	Panel horizontal (centered)	0.93	0.95
29-4-2024	13:04:56	20.9	2.3	48.07	Slight West	Tracking West	0.85	0.52
29-4-2024	14:05:13	20.6	2.1	43.26	West	Tracking West	0.77	0.78
29-4-2024	15:00:16	20.2	1.9	38.38	Facing West	Nearing West limit	0.6	0.58
29-4-2024	15:57:55	19	1.75	33.25	Facing West (steeper)	West limit reached → Stop	0.5	0.48

(West) MP 2 Status	(East) MP 4 Status	(West) Limits witch 2 Status	(East) Limit switch 4 Status
OFF (dim)	ON (bright)	OFF	ON (Pressed)
OFF	ON	OFF	OFF
ON (low)	ON	OFF	OFF
Balanced	Balanced	OFF	OFF
ON	OFF	OFF	OFF
ON (bright)	OFF (dim)	OFF	OFF
ON (bright)	OFF	OFF	OFF
ON (low)	OFF	ON (Pressed)	OFF

As the ADXL 345 measures the gravitational acceleration along the X axis , it needs to be converted into tilt for better understanding. This gravitation acceleration along the X axis is converted into degree tilt as below.

$$\theta = \arcsin (X) \times \frac{180}{\pi}$$

$$\theta = \arcsin (0.57) \times \frac{180}{\pi}$$

$$\theta \approx 0.6055 \text{ radians} \times \frac{180}{\pi}$$

$$\theta \approx 34.7^\circ \text{ (Tilt of PV Panel)}$$

The power output of a PV panel is estimated using voltage and current output measured at PV panel. It is important to measure the Power output to identify the increase in energy gain.

Let

O/P = Output to PV panel

I_o = Output Current recorded by PV panel (Amp)

= 1.62 Amp

V_o = Output Voltage recorded by PV panel (V)

= 19.50 V

Therefore,

$O/P = V_o \times I_o$

$$= 19.5 \times 1.62$$

$$= 31.59 \text{ Watt}$$

Following is the result table in which calculated values are tabulated for a day.

Table.5 Result table of Single Axis Tracker

Output Voltage (V)	Output Current (Amps)	Output Power (Watt)	Panel Status	Actual condition
19.5	1.62	31.59	Facing East	Panel tilted East, still tracking
20	1.85	37	Slight East	Tracking East
20.5	2.2	45.1	leaning towards	Tracking toward center
20.9	2.38	49.742	Horizontal (South)	Panel horizontal (centered)
20.9	2.3	48.07	Slight West	Tracking West
20.6	2.1	43.26	West	Tracking West
20.2	1.9	38.38	Facing West	Nearing West limit
19	1.75	33.25	Facing West (steeper)	West limit reached → Stop

The percentage increase in the Power out-put of the single axis tracking mechanism when compared with Fix tilt is calculated as follows.

The total output in a day for Single Axis at instant time (from 09:00 AM to 04:00 PM) as mentioned in Table.5

$$= 31.59 + 37 + 45.1 + 49.742 + 48.07 + 43.26 + 38.38 + 33.25$$

$$= 326.39 \text{ Wh}$$

The total output in a day for Fix tilt at instant time (from 09:00 AM to 04:00 PM) as mentioned in Table.3

$$= 24.83 + 31.35 + 40.24 + 44.505 + 42.58 + 36.159 + 27.104 + 19.8$$

$$= 255.64 \text{ Wh}$$

$$\text{Percentage Increase} = \frac{(\text{Single axis tracker Output} - \text{Fix Tilt Tracker Output})}{\text{Fix tilt tracker output}}$$

$$= \frac{(326.39 - 255.64)}{255.64}$$

= 27.67% (% Increase in Power output of Single axis tracking vs Fix Tilt)

6.3 Performance Evaluation of Dual Axis Tracker:-

The Quantities which are directly measured i.e Gravitation acceleration, Insolation, Mini Panel Currents using sensors are as given in Table. 6.

Table.6 Observation Table for Primary Parameters-I

Date	Time	Visible (Lux)	Temp (°C)	Pyranometer (W/m ²)	(West) MP 2 Current	(East) MP 4 Current	(North) MP 1 Current	(South) MP 3 Current
29-05-2024	9.0.1	1185	40.85	485	0.5	0.58	0.55	0.72
29-05-2024	10.0.5	1280	42.5	650	0.6	0.65	0.61	0.73
29-05-2024	11.0.23	1352	47.52	750	0.8	0.85	0.82	0.88
29-05-2024	12:04:01	1575	55.75	925	0.93	0.95	0.85	0.72
29-05-2024	13:02:00	1510	56.8	930	0.85	0.52	0.65	0.61
29-05-2024	14:04:00	1489	57.2	801	0.77	0.78	0.77	0.77
29-05-2024	15:00:02	1250	54.5	650	0.6	0.58	0.59	0.58
29-05-2024	16:00:02	1000	51.25	501	0.5	0.48	0.49	0.48

The Mini Panel status and Limit Switch status during tracking is tabulated below in Table.7.

Table.7 Mini Panel and Limit switch status.

(West) MP 2 Status	(East) MP 4 Status	(North) MP 1 Status	(South) MP 3 Status	(West) Limits witch 2 Status	(East) Limit switch 4 Status	(North) Limits witch 1 Status	(South) Limit switch 3 Status
OFF (dim)	ON (bright)	OFF (dim)	ON (bright)	OFF (Not pressed)	OFF (Not pressed)	OFF	OFF
ON (low)	ON	ON (low)	ON (bright)	OFF	OFF	OFF	OFF
ON (low)	ON	ON (low)	ON (bright)	OFF	OFF	OFF	OFF
Balanced	Balanced	Balanced	Balanced	OFF	OFF	OFF	OFF
ON	OFF	ON	Medium	OFF	OFF	OFF	OFF
ON (bright)	OFF (dim)	ON (bright)	Medium	OFF	OFF	OFF	OFF
ON (bright)	OFF (dim)	ON (bright)	Medium	OFF	OFF	OFF	OFF
ON (low)	OFF (dim)	OFF (dim)	ON (low)	OFF	ON (Pressed)	ON (Pressed)	OFF

As the ADXL 345 measures the gravitational acceleration along the X axis and Y axis it needs to be converted into tilt in degrees for better understanding. This gravitation acceleration along the X and Y axis is converted into degree tilt as below.

Calculation of tilt in X direction

$$\theta = \arcsin (x) \times \frac{180}{\pi}$$

$$\theta_x = \arcsin (0.51) \times \frac{180}{\pi} \dots \text{Where } x = 0.51 \text{ (Gravitational acceleration in X direction)}$$

$$\theta_x = 30.66^\circ \text{ (Tilt of PV Panel in X direction)}$$

Calculation of tilt in Y direction

$$\theta_y = \arcsin (y) \times \frac{180}{\pi}$$

$$\theta_y = \arcsin (0.21) \times \frac{180}{\pi} \dots \text{Where } y = 0.21 \text{ (Gravitational acceleration in Y direction)}$$

$$\theta_y = 12.12^\circ \text{ (Tilt of PV Panel in Y direction)}$$

The power output of PV Panel is estimated using voltage and current output measured at PV Panel. It is important to measure the Power output to identify the increase in energy gain.

Let

O/P = Output to PV Panel

I_o = Output Current recorded by PV Panel (Amp)

= 1.62 Amp

V_o = Output Voltage recorded by PV Panel (V)

= 19.50 V

Therefore,

O/P = $V_o \times I_o$

= 20.5×1.8

= 36.9 Watt

Following is the result table in which calculated values for a day are tabulated.

Table.8 The status of Main panel in terms of its orientation in X and Y direction

Panel Status (E-W)	Panel Status (N-S)	Output Voltage (V)	Output Current (Amps)	Output Power (Watt)
Facing East	Facing South	20.5	1.8	36.9
Slight East	South tilt decreased	20.7	1.9	39.33
leaning towards	Further decrease in south tilt	20.8	2.4	49.92
Horizontal (South)	Sun is nearly overhead (Panel lies flat)	20.9	2.65	55.385
Slight West	Tilting towards north	20.8	2.6	54.08
West	Follows Sun as it moves toward the west	20.7	2.55	52.785
Facing West	Panel tilt increases northward	20.6	2.1	43.26
Facing slightly West	Maximum north tilt	19.8	1.8	35.64

The percentage increase in the Power out-put of Dual axis tracking mechanism when compared with Fix tilt is calculated as follows.

The total output in a day for Dual axis at instant time(from 09:00 AM to 04:00 PM) as mentioned in Table.8

$$= 36.9+39.33+49.92+54.34+55.12+52.785+43.26+35.64$$

Total output in a day for Dual axis tracking = 367.29 Wh

The total output in a day for Fix tilt at instant time (from 09:00 AM to 04:00 PM) as mentioned in Table.3

$$= 24.83+31.35+40.24+44.505+42.58+36.159+27.104+19.8$$

$$= 255.64 \text{ Wh}$$

$$\text{Percentage Increase} = \frac{(\text{Dual axis tracker Output} - \text{Fix Tilt Tracker Output})}{\text{Fix tilt tracker output}}$$

$$= \frac{(367.29 - 255.64)}{255.64}$$

$$= 43.67\% \text{ (\% Increase in Power output of dual axis tracking vs fix tilt)}$$

The percentage increase in the Power out-put of Dual axis tracking mechanism when compared with Single axis is calculated as follows.

The total output in a day for Dual axis at instant time as mentioned in Table.8

$$= 367.29 \text{ Wh}$$

The total output in a day for single axis at instant time(from 09:00 AM to 04:00 PM) as mentioned in Table.5

$$= 31.89+37+45.1+49.57+48.07+43.26+38.38+33.25$$

$$= 326.39 \text{ Wh}$$

$$\text{Percentage Increase} = \frac{(\text{Dual axis tracker Output} - \text{Single Axis Tracker Output})}{\text{Single Axis Tracker Output}}$$

$$= \frac{(367.29 - 326.36)}{326.39}$$

$$= 12.54\% \text{ (\% Increase in Power output of dual axis tracking vs single axis tracking)}$$

8. Result:

The percentage rise in power output in case of dual axis tracker and Single axis tracking mechanism when compared with fix-tilt system is shown below in Table.9.

Table.9 PV Performance by Tacking System

Panel Position	Power (Watt-hr)	Gain (%)	Gain (%)
Fix Tilt	255.64	-----	-----
Single axis tracking	326.39	27.67	-----
Dual axis tracking	367.29	43.67	12.54

The numerical investigation undertaken in this study provides a comprehensive comparative assessment of various solar tracking mechanisms and their respective impacts on power output of PV panel. The results demonstrate that while single-axis trackers offer a practical balance between performance enhancement and simplicity of system. Dual-axis trackers deliver the highest energy gains by enabling optimal solar incidence throughout the day and seasons.

The graphical representation of Time vs Solar Insolation (W/m^2) is given below in figure.10. Solar insolation is measured by Silicon Pyranometer as discussed in section 4.2. It clearly shows that in the morning, the sun is low on the horizonhence the value of solar insolation is

less. At noon the Sun is exactly overhead therefore the value of solar insolation is high. Similarly, in the evening time sun approaches horizon therefore the value of solar insolation is less.

Figure.10 Time vs Solar Insolation (Fix tilt, Single axis & dual axis)

The graphical representation of Time vs Power (Watt) is given below in figure.1. The Power Output of PV Panel is calculated in section 6.1 , 6.2 & 6.3 for Fix tilt , Single axis and Dual axis respectively.

Figure.11 Time vs Power Output (Fix tilt, Single axis & dual axis)

9. Conclusion:

The percentage rise in power output in case of Single axis tracking system when compared with fix tilt was found out to be 27.67% which is higher than that of what cited in literature i.e 6.41 % to 20%. The percentage rise in power output in case of Dual axis tracking system when compared with fix tilt was found out to be 43.67% which is higher than that of what cited in literature i.e 13% to 36.26%.

The percentage rise in power output in case of Dual axis tracking system when compared with single axis tracking was found out to be 12.54% which is higher than that of what cited in literature i.e 1.14 % to 8.21 %.

This study compares three types of solar tracking systems: fix-tilt, single-axis, dual-axis and testing was carried out to measure how well they perform. The results highlighted that Dual axis trackers outsmarts in performance than other types as mentioned in section 6. The fix-tilt systems are easy to use as compared to single and dual axis systems. But a fix-tilt collector cannot collect the maximum amount of solar energy throughout the year. Dual-axis trackers are more complex however they can produce more energy by always pointing the solar panels at the sun from different angles.

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